

Appendix 3. The six plain language summaries

1. "GRADE" overall uncertainty with margin of error

What are the effects of wearing glasses to reduce the chance of getting Covid?

What is the benefit?

Wearing glasses may slightly reduce your chance of getting Covid (⊕⊕○○ [low certainty evidence](#)).

What are the downsides?

Wearing glasses probably does not increase your chance of any major harms, such as a serious fall due to reduced vision (⊕⊕⊕○ [moderate certainty evidence](#)). But some people are irritated by foggy glasses, and some feel silly wearing them.

What is the evidence?

What was known?

Some researchers thought wearing glasses might protect against Covid infection – but the evidence was limited. A [recent systematic review](#) of studies examined whether eye protection – including glasses - protects against Covid infection. The review found that it might make a difference. But the studies were not [randomized studies](#). This means that the findings might be explained by differences in the people who happened to wear glasses rather than any effect glasses might have.

What's new?

A [new randomized study](#) has been published. Based on the flip of a coin, about 3800 healthy adults were told either to wear glasses when around others, or not to wear them.

Here's what happened:

BENEFIT

Over the next 2 weeks, slightly fewer people told to wear glasses tested positive for COVID: 9.6% compared to 11.5% of those told not to wear glasses. That's a difference of 1.9%.

Accounting for the play of chance (i.e., the [margin of error](#)), glasses might *reduce* the risk of Covid by as much as 3.9% but might *increase* it by as much as 0.1%.

DOWNSIDES

There were no major harms linked to wearing glasses. One person reported a fall due to reduced vision, and about 25 people (0.2%) reported being irritated by foggy glasses, especially when also wearing a face mask.

Keep in mind

Wearing glasses may slightly reduce your chance of getting Covid – but we are not very confident about this. This is because of the wide [margin of error](#) and important [study limitations](#):

- *People knew if they were told to wear glasses* (i.e., the study was not [blinded](#)). This may have led them to behave differently and do other things (which they were not told to do) that might affect their chance of Covid infection. In fact, we know that people in the glasses group were more likely to wear face masks - which might have reduced Covid risk. Being told to wear glasses also might have affected how often people tested themselves for Covid or reported a positive result.
- *The results might not [apply](#) to you.* Covid infection rates were very high in this trial where 11.5% of people got Covid over 2 weeks, meaning there was a big surge at that time. The difference between wearing and not wearing glasses would be less if Covid levels are lower where you are than in this trial.
- *Some people who were meant to wear glasses didn't* (or wore them inconsistently or for less than 2 weeks), *and some told not to wear glasses wore them anyway.* The effect of glasses might be bigger than what the study found for people who wear glasses consistently compared to not wearing glasses at all.

What to do?

It's reasonable to try glasses to protect against Covid: there may be some benefit and there are no obvious important harms. So, you might choose to wear glasses if Covid levels are high like in this trial, you are a more cautious person, or you are at more risk of developing serious illness from Covid.

You might choose not to if these do not apply, if glasses are uncomfortable or interfere with mask use, or if you simply don't have access to them.

2. "GRADE" overall uncertainty without margin of error

What are the effects of wearing glasses to reduce the chance of getting Covid?

What is the benefit?

Wearing glasses may slightly reduce your chance of getting Covid (⊕⊕○○ [low certainty evidence](#)).

What are the downsides?

Wearing glasses probably does not increase your chance of any major harms, such as a serious fall due to reduced vision (⊕⊕⊕○ [moderate certainty evidence](#)). But some people are irritated by foggy glasses, and some feel silly wearing them.

What is the evidence?

What was known?

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3. “Colloquial” overall uncertainty with margin of error

What are the effects of wearing glasses to reduce the chance of getting Covid?

What is the benefit?

Wearing glasses may reduce your chance of getting Covid a little – but we are not very confident about this.

What are the downsides?

We are somewhat confident that wearing glasses does not cause important harms such as a serious fall due to reduced vision. But some people are irritated by foggy glasses, and some feel silly wearing them.

What is the evidence?

What was known?

Some researchers thought wearing glasses might protect against Covid infection – but the evidence was limited. A [recent systematic review](#) of studies examined whether eye protection – including glasses - protects against Covid infection. The review found that it might make a difference. But the studies were not [randomized studies](#). This means that the findings might be explained by differences in the people who happened to wear glasses rather than any effect glasses might have.

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4. “Colloquial” overall uncertainty without margin of error

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What are the downsides?

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What is the evidence?

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You might choose not to if these do not apply, if glasses are uncomfortable or interfere with mask use, or if you simply don't have access to them.

5. No overall uncertainty with margin of error

What are the effects of wearing glasses to reduce the chance of getting Covid?

What is the benefit?

Wearing glasses may reduce your chance of getting Covid a little.

What are the downsides?

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What is the evidence?

What was known?

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You might choose not to if these do not apply, if glasses are uncomfortable or interfere with mask use, or if you simply don't have access to them.

6. No overall uncertainty without margin of error

What are the effects of wearing glasses to reduce the chance of getting Covid?

What is the benefit?

Wearing glasses may reduce your chance of getting Covid a little – but we are not very confident about this.

What are the downsides?

We are pretty confident that wearing glasses does not cause important harms such as a serious fall due to reduced vision. But some people are irritated by foggy glasses, and some feel silly wearing them.

What is the evidence?

What was known?

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